

The Impact of Civil Disobedience Movement in Kallakurichi District, Tamil Nadu – A Study

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ABSTRACT

This article has focused to reveal the impact of civil disobedience movement in Kallakurichi District, Tamil Nadu. The Kallakurichi District played a Role in the Freedom Movement since 1927 Participated and organized a number of anti-British protests. They Underwent imprisonment and suffered a lot. Here below traced their Involvement in the Freedom Movement. This article has focused to reveal the impact of civil disobedience movement in Kallakurichi District, Tamil Nadu. In Kallakurichi District during 1930-34 in total 24 Congressmen were arrested. They were detained in Tiruchirappalli, Cuddalore, Vellore, Cannanore and Madras Jails. The Congressmen of the Kallakurichi District actively organized and actively participated in salt Satyagraha, boycott and temperance agitations. Indeed, the above the list was witnessed the participation of people in Kallakurichi district involved in Civil Disobedience Movement like other districts.

Keywords: Freedom Movement, Civil Disobedience Movement, Salt Satyagraha, Kallakurichi district, Anti-British protest.

Introduction

Freedom movement is the crucial movement in the history of India, while people united themselves to fight for centuries in the path of Independence. There were lot of events concluded for ignition of the freedom movement and whistle blowing the freedom thoughts to achieve the goal. While Mahatma Gandhi had involved in the freedom movement has changed the route of freedom movement. Indeed, people from rural and urban background were completely involved in the movement voluntarily. Because Gandhi's speech, innovative events, plans were admired the people to involve the freedom movement. Also his movement was impacted all over India, and contributing for utilizing the same movement as a tool in the freedom movement. On the path, there were some areas were not sung by the scholars and vanished the history of freedom movement in India and Tamil Nadu. Before Independence, Tamil Nadu has been renowned as South Arcot District, where people had been participated the freedom movement in high esteem. South Arcot District has been segregated into three districts namely Cuddalore, Villupuram and Kallakurichi district. The Kallakurichi District played a Role in the Freedom Movement since 1927 Participated and organized a number of anti-British protests. They Underwent imprisonment and suffered a lot. Here below traced their Involvement in the Freedom Movement. This article has focused to reveal the impact of civil disobedience movement in Kallakurichi District, Tamil Nadu.

Civil Disobedience Movement, 1930-34

Gandhi suspended the non-cooperation movement in 1922 due to the Chuwri-Chaura incident in which twenty two police men were burnt alive due to the attack on police station by an unruly mob. Then the Indian National Congress devoted its time in constructive programmes like prohibition, popularising kadhi, explaining the evils of untouchability etc.¹ Meanwhile the Indian National Congress in its session at Madras in 1927 resolved that Complete Independence as the goal of India.² Then Gandhi start with, Purnaswaraj Day was celebrated with enthusiasm all over Tamilnadu. On the occasion of the celebration, meetings processions, door to door propaganda, and the like were organised both in cities and towns all over India including Tamilnadu.

Lahore Session held in 1929 Congress adopted a resolution that independence was the goal of India. It also decided to observe the 26th of January as the day of complete independence. Jawaharlal Nehru, the president of the Congress, hoisted the tricolor flag of independence at Lahore on the bank of the Ravi.³ A resolution moved by M.K. Gandhi demanded the reduction of land tax, prohibition of liquor and abolition of Salt Tax. However the British Government rejected these demands. In protest against the attitude of the British and for the attainment of independence the Congress working committee called upon the people to organize and undertake Civil Disobedience.

Tamil Nadu has involved more forceful in the Civil Disobedience Movement. For the support and enthusiastic effort of the S.Sathyamurthi, president of Tamil Nadu Congress Committee, the movement was successfully preceded. In Madras the city boycott committee directed the picketing of shops and boycott of foreign goods. C. Rajagopalachari and hundred volunteers staged their famous March from Tiruchirappalli to Vedaranniyam on 13th April, 1930. The March began to the accompaniment of hymns and the blessings of a priest. Triumphant reception had been planned by K. Santhanam. The masses responded in a marvelous manner. The marchers reached Vedaranniyam on 28th April and a camp was established there. Two days later C. Rajagopalachari was arrested for violating the salt laws. Also at Madras, Cuddalore,⁴ Sholinganallur,⁵ Virudunagar,⁶ Rameswaram and other places, the salt Satyagraha campaign was particularly intensive.

Temperance agitations were widespread throughout the Tamil districts but intensive in Coimbatore and Madurai districts. Picketing of foreign cloth shops was successful in almost all the towns. In almost all districts, including Madras city, labour strikes in mills and factories were organised. No-tax campaign was carried on in Madras. In total the movement spread into all the Tamil districts, but flourished in a splendid manner in Madras, Madurai, Coimbatore, Tirunelveli, Tiruchirappalli, South Arcot, North Arcot, Ramnad and Chenglepet districts.

In January 1932 the Government struck again, arrested Gandhi and other Congress leaders and declared the Congress an illegal organization. However the Civil Disobedience Movement gained more popularity and more than 1 lakh persons courted arrest. In 1933 Gandhi

confessed failure of the movement and resigned his membership of the Congress. Between 1928 and 1934, the congress movement made great confidence and determination to the people on the path of unity. Indeed, Congress has made tremendous effort with the mass participation above the movement.

Civil Disobedience Movement in kallakurichi District

The Calcutta Session of Indian National Congress held in December 1928, demanded Dominion Status for India and resolved that if this was not granted by the British government to launch a Civil Disobedience Movement.⁷ In the annual session held at Lahore in December 1929 under the chairmanship of Jawaharlal Nehru, it was also decided to launch the Civil Disobedience Movement for the attainment of complete independence. The programmes of the Civil Disobedience Movement included salt Satyagraha, boycott, khadar propaganda and anti-liquor agitations.⁸

Purna Swaraj Day Celebration

The Civil Disobedience Movement was started with the Celebration of Purna Swaraj Day on 26 January 1930; Purna Swaraj Day was celebrated all throughout the country.⁹ In Tamil Nadu the Day was observed with much enthusiasm. In Kallakurichi, the Congress people organised meetings and prayers on that day. They also indulged in door-to-door Congress propaganda.¹⁰

Salt Satyagraha

The Congress people of Kallakurichi District organised a Number of programmes in support of Salt Satyagraha during 1930-34. And also partook in Devanampatnam Salt Satyagraha. The local Leaders of the South Arcot District notably Nainiappa Pillai and Sudarsana Naidu were much inspired by the Gandhi's Dandi March and proposed to start a similar one in their district itself in April 1930. They decided to start a mass salt Satyagraha at Devanampatnam, a Coastal village situated two kilometers away from Cuddalore New Town.¹¹

Nainiappa Pillai and his associates began to concentrate on conducting a salt Satyagraha at Devanampatnam since April 1930. They mobilized support from the people all over Tamil Nadu. They visited Kallakurichi not only to propagate about the proposed Satyagraha, but also to seek the support of the people there. Nainiappa Pillai along with twenty volunteers including Narayanasamy Naidu of Kallakurichi,¹² Vadivalupather, goldsmith, Balaraman of Virudhachalam and Krishnamurthy, teacher, started to march Towards Devanampatnam covering a distance of fifty kilometers from Chidambaram. They traversed about sixteen kilometers per day and Reached Cuddalore on the third day on the morning of April 16, 1930.

On 16th April the satyagrahis, under the inspiration of Nainiappa Pillai, Sudarsana Naidu and Kumarasami Pillai and others broke the Salt Law by boiling sea water. Almost every day they tried to manufacture salt, but were persistently harassed by the police and Salt peons.¹³ On the morning of 17th April, under the leadership of Nainiappa Pillai, a lot of volunteers including C. Ramasamy Chettiar, Arumugamudaliar, son of Cheinnaiah of Kallakurichi District¹⁴ went to Devanampatnam seashore and attempted to prepare salt by boiling Sea water. Arumuga Mudaliar was arrested and convicted for six Months in Trichirappalli Jail. C, Ramasamy Chettiar of Kallakurichi was also arrested under Section 188 of Indian Penal Code and Imprisoned at Coimbatore and Trichirappalli Jails for four months.

There was a meeting held on the evening of 17.4.1930 at river Gadilam dry bed. Nainiappa Pillai addressed the meeting. He said “Englishmen were sticking to India like leeches and just leeches could be removed only by putting salt on them. The salt Satyagraha was the only remedy to get Englishmen to leave India. About 200 people attended the meeting. It is said that T.N. Rajamanickam native of Kallakurichi also attended the meeting He was arrested and imprisoned. The salt Satyagraha attained much strength towards the end of April. On 22 April, the satyagrahis went to the shore in different batches. The first batch, led by Nainiappa Pillai, was full of fisher boys. The boys boiled the brine. Another batch led by Tailor Balaraman of Virudhachalam consisting of P. Ramdoss Naidu of Kallakurichi town and others, K.Seethapathi Naidus of Kamala Nehru street in Kallakurichi broke the Salt Law with a number of volunteers. Ramdoss Naidu was arrested and sentenced to six months at Thirukoilur Jail.

Boycott, Swadeshi and Prohibition Movements

Boycott, swadeshi, and prohibition programmes were popularized all over Kallakurichi District. Various methods of propagation were carried on advocating the use of swadeshi goods, the boycott of foreign goods and the evils of drinking of toddy and others liquors. On 28 February 1932, O.P. Ramasamy and his associate held a meeting at Kallakurichi Town. They explained of civil disobedience ideologies and condemned the police repression. During the deliberations of the meeting a police party intervened and attempted to disperse the audience by administering lathi charges. But the audience refused to vacate the spot and pelted stones on the party. Enraged at this, the police arrested T.S. Swaminatha Iyer and sent to the nearby the police station. In the station he was assaulted by the police.

In March 1932, the Congress volunteers of Kallakurichi like Duraisami Moopan and others collected foreign clothes from the public and set them fire. For that Duraisami Moopan was arrested under Section 17(1) of Criminal Law and imprisoned for six months at Cuddalore and Trichirappalli Jails. On 11 July 1932, K.A. NatesaMudaliar of Chinnasalem and Ramasamy of Thimmayapuram, along with some Congress volunteers went to Chinnasalem and advised the people to boycott the foreign clothes and burnt some foreign clothes in the street. Natesa Mudaliar and Ramasamy were arrested and imprisoned for six months each at Tiruchirappalli Jail.

In Chinnasalem the Congress volunteers like S. Govindan, son of SingaraveluKounder, Gopalsami Naidu and others continued to propagate against foreign cloths and shouted anti-British slogans. The volunteers dissuaded the people not to purchase foreign clothes. They also pleaded the people to wear only Khadhar. They also burnt foreign clothes collected from the Congress supporters of this District in connection with this S.Govindan and Gopalsami were arrested and Sentenced to six months each at Tiruchirappalli and Cannanore Jails. At Thimmayapuram, a village in Kallakurichi District, the Local Congress men such as K.Chinnasamy, son of Nachimuthu, and Ramasamy an agriculturist, both belonged to the middle class families Carried on ardent swadeshi preaching. They used to visit almost all the houses in

the village and emphasized that the people should wear Khadhar only. In connection with this K.Chinnasamy was arrested and imprisoned for six months at Trichirappalli Jails.

In March 1933, the local Congress people organised a Political propaganda meeting in Kallakurichi. Narayanasamy Naidu¹⁵ Ramalinga Mudaliar of Seruppakkam and ArumugaMudaliar of Chinnasalem the organizers of the meeting were arrested and Sentenced to six months imprisonment each and were put in Central Jail at Trichirappalli, In Kallakurichi District the temperance agitation was Intensive and such agitations were organised very often. In 1932 the Congress volunteers of the District picketed liquor shops in Kallakurichi and Chinnasalem. To mobilise mass support as well as to highlight the evils of drinking, door to door propaganda were in the Congress men of area also organised meetings and processions advocating the evils of drinking.

On 5th February 1932, some of the Congress people of Kallakurichi District picketed a toddy shop. One of the posters K. PalanimuthuMudaliar of Chinnasalem was arrested and sentenced to six months at Cuddalore and Trichirappalli Jails. The campaign continued in March 1932. At Movannajor near Kallakurichi the local Congressmen of the village namely M.Pavadai son of Muthu picketed a toddy shop in the village He Became violent and assaulted the owner of the shop and destroyed the Toddy pots and furniture. M.Pavadai was arrested and imprisoned for Six months at Madras Jail". The police arrest to suppress the Agitators was widely condemned.

Conclusion

In Kallakurichi the Congress workers like E.Rathinam, son Of ElappaChetty, B.S. Subbunarayanan and T.V. Perumal organised Processions advocating temperance in their areas. They along with a large number of volunteers picketed a number of toddy shops. E. Rathinam and T.V. Perumal were arrested and convicted for six Months each and put at Cuddalore, Cannanore and Madras Jails, B.S. Subbunarayanan was also arrested under Section 188, Indian Penal Code and under Section 4 of Ordinance Act and sentenced to 9 months and put at Cuddalore, Bellary and Madras Central Jails. By the end of the year 1932, K. Ramaswami Moopan of Thimmayapuram and his men picketed a toddy shop located near try Kallakurichi

town. The police arrested K.Ramaswami under Section 17(1) of Criminal Law Amendment Act and imprisoned him at Cuddalore and Trichirappalli Central Jails for six months, In April 1933, Thirumalai of Chinnasalem, Vaiyapuri Mudaliar, son of Munia Mudaliar organised propaganda procession and went to toddy shops and advised the consumers not to drink toddy. For that they were arrested under Section 17(1) of Criminal Law Amendment Act and sentenced to six month each at Tiruchirappalli Jail.

List of persons have arrested during Civil Disobedience Movement in Kallakurichi District.

SL. No	Freedom Fighters	Native Place	Imprisonment Period	Jail
1	Arumugm.C	Chinnasalem	5 months	Tiruchirappalli
2	Chinnasamy.N	Thimmayapuram	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
3	Doraisami	Tirukoilur	6 months	Vellore
4	Duraisami.A	kallakurichi	7 months	Cuddalore& Tiruchirappalli
5	Ganesan	Tirukoilur	6 months	Vellore
6	Gopalsami.K	Chinnasalem	6 months	Cannanore
7	Govinda Rao	Thiruvonnainallur	6 months	Alipuram, Cuddalore, Madras, Bellary
8	Govindan.S	Chinnasalem	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
9	Krishnaya.R	kallakurichi	6 months	Tanjore
10	Madura	Tirukoilur	6 months	Cuddalore& Bellary
11	Mahadeva	Tirukoilur	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
12	Naraynasamy.K	kallakurichi	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
13	Natesan .K.A	Chinnasalem	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
14	Palanimuthu	Chinnasalem	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
15	Pavadai.M	Mo. Vannajure	6 months	Madras
16	Ramasami .G	Tirukoilur	6 months	Vellore, Alipuram
17	Ramasamy	Thimmayapuram	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
18	Ramasamy	kallakurichi	4 months	Madras
19	Ramaswami	Thimmayapuram	6 months	Cuddalore, Tiruchirappalli
20	Rathinam	kallakurichi	6 months	Cuddalore, Cannanore
21	Subburayan.S	kallakurichi	9 months	Cuddalore, Bellary, Madras
22	Swaminathan.T.S	kallakurichi	1 year	Tiruchirappalli
23	Thirumalai	Chinnasalem	6 months	Tiruchirappalli
24	Vaiyapuri	Chinnasalem	6 months	Tiruchirappalli

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